

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**THE STUDY OF CERVICAL RIB ASSOCIATION WITH TOS
(THORACIC OUTLET SYNDROME) IN PAKISTANI
POPULATION**

¹Sajjad Tassawar, ²Rana Muhammad Farooq Sattar, ³Muhammad Haji
¹Nishtar Medical University, Multan., ²Nishtar Medical University, Multan., ³Independent
Medical College, Faisalabad.

Abstract:

Objective: This study's main objective is to determine the link between a cervical rib and thoracic outlet syndrome in the population of Pakistan.

Design and duration: the study is of observational type, and the duration of the study is 12 months from May 2019 to April 2019.

Settings: the study was conducted in the surgical ward of Nishtar Hospital Multan.

Patients and methods: Patients reporting symptoms of thoracic outlet syndrome in the hospital were tested for cervical rib using x-rays and MRI CT scans. Convenience sampling techniques have been used. Patients from both genders of different ages were included in the study. All the data were calculated in a pre-designed performa, and data were analyzed using SPSS version 24 and presented via tables and graphs. The confidence interval was 95%, with a 5% error margin. Less than 0.05 P-value was considered to be relevant.

Results: a total of 180 thoracic outlet syndrome cases, including 68(37.8%) male and 112(62.2 per cent) female patients were reported. In 14(7.8 per cent cases), the cervical rib was present. One hundred fifty-nine patients were reported with numbness on the medial side of the forearm and hand. 8(57.1%) of the patients with cervical rib were treated with surgical excision, while six were treated with conservative treatment with analgesics. Analgesics and anxiolytics were given to 141 patients who have thoracic outlet syndrome and not having cervical ribs (166 patients), and nerve conduction studies were done in 25 patients.

Conclusion: Past, clinical evaluation, and verified radiological examination and neurophysiological tests are used to diagnose thoracic outlet syndrome. The treatment of TOS depends on the case of TOS. In most cases, patients are cured only with conservative therapy, and surgical therapy is indicated only if conservative therapy fails.

Corresponding author:

Sajjad Tassawar,
Nishtar Medical University, Multan.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Sajjad Tassawar et al, *The Study Of Cervical RIB Association With TOS (Thoracic Outlet Syndrome) In Pakistani Population.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Thoracic outlet syndrome includes neurological and vascular systems, so paresthesia, numbness of the forearm and hands, and vascular insufficiency can occur in patients with this syndrome. Most patients suffer from numbness in their hands. There is a need for diagnostic history and clinical evaluation accompanied by neurophysiological examination. On scheduled x-rays, MRI, and Ct scans, diagnosis may be confirmed. It is possible to rule out either neurological or vascular causes of symptoms through these inquiries. In our population, this condition is growing. There are primarily females involved. Patients can also experience neck pain, mandibular pain, or shoulder-area pain. They were exaggerating symptoms when doing work. In our community, the cervical rib is a common cause of TOS. It is a congenital disorder in which the seventh cervical vertebrae are the origins of the first rib. The rib may be attached by a fibrous band, cartilage, or bone to the vertebrae, particularly on the right side. It is on the left side occasionally, or even bilateral. It remains asymptomatic until the pressure in the thoracic outlet occurs on the brachial plexus or vessels.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

this study is completed in one year and is of observational type. The study was held in a tertiary care hospital, Nishtar Hospital Multan. Appropriate sampling techniques have been used. Patients reporting thoracic outlet syndrome symptoms in the research hospital were tested for cervical rib using x-rays and MRI CT scans. Convenience sampling techniques have been used. Patients, regardless of

gender and age, were included. The data were calculated in a pre-designed performa, and data were analyzed using SPSS version 24 and presented via tables and graphs. The confidence interval was 95%, with a 5% error margin. The P-value was found to be less than 0.05. Informed consent (IC) was obtained from all cases in the research community, and the hospital's ethical committee before performing the study. Privacy of data has been assured. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were formed according to which patients with signs and symptoms of thoracic outlet syndrome confirmed on nerve conduction tests and radiographs were included in the study. The research did not involve patients who did not have a good history, non-cooperative, who did not have other causes of distal numbness other than TOS, and those who disagreed.

RESULTS:

a total of 180 thoracic outlet syndrome cases, including 68(37.8%) male and 112(62.2 per cent) female patients were reported. In 14(7.8 per cent cases), the cervical rib was present. One hundred fifty-nine patients were reported with numbness on the medial side of the forearm and hand. 8(57.1%) of the patients with cervical rib were treated with surgical excision, while six were treated with conservative treatment with analgesics. Analgesics and anxiolytics were given to 141 patients who have thoracic outlet syndrome and not having cervical ribs (166 patients), and nerve conduction studies were done in 25 patients. The patients with TOS symptoms were between 15 to 55 years of age, with a mean age of 28.4 ± 7.6 years. Most patients were between the ages of 20-30.

DISCUSSION:

In Pakistan, thoracic outlet syndrome is growing in prevalence, and the cervical rib is the most common cause in our population. Numbness of the hand, muscle wasting of the hand, radiating pain to the throat, jaw, and shoulder may be present. Neurological and vascular systems are involved in thoracic outlet syndrome, so patients with this syndrome may have paresthesia, forearm and hand numbness, and vascular insufficiency. Most patients suffer from numbness in their hands. There is a need for diagnostic history and clinical review accompanied by neurophysiological examination. It is possible to confirm a diagnosis on X-rays, MRI, and Ct scans of the plan. Through these tests, neurological or vascular causes of symptoms may be eliminated. In our population, this condition is growing. There are primarily females involved. Patients can also experience neck pain, mandibular pain, or shoulder-area pain. They were exaggerating symptoms when doing work. This is an observational study conducted over one year. It was performed at the Nishtar Hospital Multan, a tertiary care hospital.

Convenience sampling techniques have been used. Patients reporting thoracic outlet syndrome symptoms in the research hospital were tested for cervical rib using x-rays and MRI CT scans. Convenience sampling techniques have been used. Patients, regardless of gender and age, were included. All the data were calculated in a pre-designed performa, and data were analyzed using SPSS version 24 and presented via tables and graphs. A total of 180 thoracic outlet syndrome cases, including 68(37.8%) male and 112(62.2 per cent) female patients were reported. In 14(7.8 per cent cases), the cervical rib was present. One hundred fifty-nine patients were reported with numbness on the medial side of the forearm and hand. 8(57.1%) of the patients with cervical rib were treated with surgical excision, while six were treated with conservative treatment with analgesics. It is a congenital disorder in which the seventh cervical vertebrae is the origin of the first rib. The rib may be attached by a fibrous band, cartilage, or bone to the vertebrae, particularly on the right side. It is on the left side occasionally, or even bilateral. It remains asymptomatic until the pressure in the thoracic outlet on the brachial plexus or vessels occurs. Not all TOS symptoms need to be present in the same patient, but that only one or two may be present, and in individual patients, it may be asymptomatic.

CONCLUSION:

Past, clinical evaluation, and verified radiological examination and neurophysiological tests are used to diagnose thoracic outlet syndrome. The treatment of

TOS depends on the case of TOS. In most cases, patients are cured only with conservative therapy, and surgical therapy is indicated only if conservative therapy fails.

REFERENCES:

1. Koknel Talu G. Thoracic outlet syndrome. *Agri*. 2005; 17:5–9.
2. Campbell WW, Landau ME. Controversial entrapment neuropathies. *Neurosurg Clin N Am*. 2008; 19:597–608, using neurogenic thoracic outlet syndrome. *J Vasc Surg* 2002; 36: 51-6.
3. Samarasam I, Sadhu D, Agarwal S, Nayak S. Surgical management of thoracic outlet syndrome: a 10-year experience. *ANZ J Surg*. 2004; 74:450–4.
4. Sanders RJ, Hammond SL, Rao NM. Diagnosis of thoracic outlet syndrome. *J Vasc Surg*. 2007; 46:601–4.
5. Pollack EW. Surgical anatomy of the thoracic outlet syndrome. *Surg Gynecol Obstet*. 1980; 150:97–103.
6. Khan A, Rattihalli RR, Hussain N. Bilateral thoracic outlet syndrome: An uncommon presentation of a rare condition in children. *Ann Indian Acad Neurol*. 2012 Oct 15(4):323-5. doi: 10.4103/0972-2327.104349.
7. Hooper TL, Denton J, Mc Galliard MK, et al; Thoracic outlet syndrome: a controversial clinical condition. Part 1: anatomy, and clinical examination/diagnosis. *J Man Manip Ther*. 2010 Jun 18(2):74-83.
8. Demondion X, Herbinet P, van Sint Jan S, Boutry N, Chantelot C, Cotten A. Imaging assessment of thoracic outlet syndrome. *Radiographics*. 2006; 26:1735–50.
9. Sheth RN, Belzberg AJ. Diagnosis and treatment of thoracic outlet syndrome. *Neurosurg Clin N Am*. 2001 Apr; 12(2):295-30.
10. Sanders RJ, Hammond SL. Management of cervical ribs and anomalous first ribs.
11. Sanders RJ, Hammond SL. Management of cervical ribs and anomalous first ribs causing neurogenic thoracic outlet syndrome. *JVasc Surg*. 2002 Jul; 36(1):51.
12. Chang KZ, Likes K, Davis K, Demos J, Freischlag JA. The significance of cervical ribs in thoracic outlet syndrome. *JVasc Surg*. 2013; 57(3):771.

13. Wise R. Seventh cervical rib associated with subclavian artery occlusion and multiple infarcts: case report. *J Neurosci Nurs*. 2008; 40(3):169-72.
14. Morbidelli A, Miani S, Bortolani E. Complete cervical rib. Possible neurovascular implications of the upper limb]. *Minerva Chir*. 1989; 15; 44(7):1167-72.
15. Merks JHM, Smets AM, Van Rijn RR, Kobes JCHN, Maas M, Hennekam RC. Prevalence of rib anomalies in normal Caucasian children and childhood cancer patients. *Eur J Med Gen* 2005; 48:113-29.
16. Plaza Aulestia N, Rodríguez Montero S, Velloso Feijoo ML. Double cervical rib: A case report. *Reumatol Clin*. 2017 Jul 31. pii: S1699-258X(17)30175-4.
17. Viertel VG, Intrapromkul J, Maluf F, Patel NV, Zheng W, Alluwaimi F, et al. Cervical ribs: a common variant overlooked in CT imaging. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 2012; 33:2191-2194.
18. Nord KM, Kapoor P, Fisher J. False positive rate of thoracic outlet syndrome diagnostic maneuvers. *Electromyogr Clin Neurophysiol*. 2008 Mar 48(2):67-74.
19. Roos DB. Historical perspectives and anatomic considerations. Thoracic outlet syndrome. *Semin Thorac Cardiovasc Surg*. 1996 Apr; 8(2):183-9.
20. Sizer PS Jr1, Phelps V, Brismee JM. Differential diagnosis of local cervical syndrome versus cervical brachial syndrome. *Pain Pract*. 2001 Jan; 1(1):21-35.
21. Klaassen Z, Sorenson E, Tubbs RS. Thoracic outlet syndrome: a neurological and vascular disorder. *Clin Anat*. 2014 Jul; 27(5):724-32.
22. Song WC, Kim SH, Park DK, Koh KS. Bifid rib: anatomical considerations in three cases. *Yonsei Med J* 2009; 50: 300-3.
23. Verna E, Piercecchi-Marti MD, Chaumoitre K, Bartoli C, Leonetti G, Adalian P Discrete traits of the sternum and ribs: a useful contribution to identification in forensic anthropology and medicine. *J Forensic Sci*. 2013 May; 58(3):571-7.
24. El-Busaid H, Kaisha W, Hassanali J, Hassan S, Ogeng'o J, Mandela P. Sternal foramina and variant xiphoid morphology in a Kenyan population. *FoliaMorphol (Warsz)*. 2012 Feb; 71(1):19-2.
25. Yekeler E, Tunaci M, Tunaci A, Dursun M, AcunasG. Frequency of sternal variations and anomalies evaluated by MDCT. *AJR Am J Roentgenol*. 2006 Apr; 186(4):956-60.
26. GockelM. Operative treatment of thoracic outlet syndrome in Finland. *Ann ChirGynaecol*. 1996; 85(1):59-61.
27. Degeorges R, Reynaud C, Becquemin JP. Thoracic outlet syndrome surgery: long-term functional results. *Ann Vasc Surg*. 2004 Sep; 18(5):558-65.
28. Sanders RJ, Hammond SL. Supraclavicular total scalenectomy with or without first rib resection: technic and results. *Handchir Mikrochir Plast Chir*. 2006 Feb; 38(1):29-3.
29. Sanders RJ, Hammond SL. Supraclavicular first rib resection and total scalenectomy: technique and results. *HandClin*. 2004 Feb; 20(1):61-70.
30. Atasoy E Combined surgical treatment of thoracic outlet syndrome: transaxillary first rib resection and transcervicalscalenectomy. *Hand Clin*. 2004 Feb; 20(1):71-82.
31. Belmin J, Valensi P. Diabetic neuropathy in elderly patients. What can be done? *Drugs Aging*. 1996 Jun; 8(6):416-2.
32. Rota E, Morelli N. Entrapment neuropathies in diabetes mellitus. *World J Diabetes*. 2016 Sep 15; 7(17):342-53.